

APPLICATION OF X-WEB TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVED SHEAR TRANSFER IN WIND TURBINE BLADES UPWARDS OF 100 METERS

R. Barnhart^{1*}, K. Wetzel¹

¹ Wetzel Engineering Inc., Wind Energy, Lawrence, KS, USA,

* Corresponding author (rmb@wetzelengineering.com)

Keywords: *X-Web, Shear Transfer, Less Core, Efficient Structures, Wind Turbine*

1 General Introduction

Wind turbine rotor blades that use a conventional single shear-web design (Fig. 1a) or a pair of distinct webs (Figure 1b [1]) are proving structurally inefficient with the spanwise growth of the blade. These webs are designed to carry the shear between blade shells during deflection. Often this requires the use of thick core in a sandwich structure to prevent web buckling itself.

The flanges in a traditional design such as this are *intended* to spread the lap shear across the bonded member and transfer the shear to the face sheets. These flanges have proven to be relatively ineffective, resulting in lap shear stress in the bond concentrated near the web face sheets, which may promote de-bonding.

2 Introduction of Efficiency Alternatives

2.1 Gross Shear Flow

The problem at hand is gross shear flow from the pressure surface to the suction surface (or vice versa) during operation. Significant amounts of shear need to be transferred due to the overall deflection of the blade under load. Since the problem at hand is not a simple vertical shear web (or set of vertical webs), the shear flow magnitude is dependent on the twist of the blade and the deflection at that cross-section. If a twisted web is required, the manufacturing complexity is amplified. A more gradual transitional shear path from the shell to the web is needed for more efficient flow of load than in current designs. This can be achieved through manipulation of the angles of the x-web design. Through careful planning, manufacturing complexity may be reduced in an x-web configuration. Fig. 2 shows the shear flow in a traditional design [2].

2.2 Shell Buckling

These webs, although it may seem counter-intuitive, also have adverse effects on shell buckling. There are now very few shear transfer mechanisms due to weight concerns. The stiffness of these structures is often very high - inefficiently spreading the buckling resistance across a wide enough extent. The x-web configuration proposed in this paper alleviates that sudden change in stiffness, resulting in fewer opportunities for shell buckling.

2.3 Web Buckling

The webs carry large loads as a result of trying to use them for resisting buckling of the shells such that they need thick core between the face sheets to prevent buckling of the web itself. The core is costly and adds unnecessary amounts of weight if an alternative can be developed. It is hard on quality control due to the difficulties of managing resin uptake in the core materials.

3. The Proposed X-Web Solution

Fig. 3 shows the solution that is proposed to resolve the disadvantages addressed in the previous sections.

3.1 Gradual Shear Flow

Due to the shape of the web, the closed section shear flow paths are more in-line with that of the open section shear flow. This allows more shear from both the leading edge (LE) and trailing edge (TE) to enter the web points gradually since the webs are separated by a much greater distance and the bond line is wider. This results in a reduction in LE and TE bond lap shear and panel buckling (See Section 3.2) as well. Fig. 4 shows the shear flow in the x-web design.

3.2 Panel Buckling Relief

The separation of the shear paths also allows the cross section to “breathe” much more than would

normally be encountered during operations. This reduces the chances of LE and TE panel buckling due to a lower stiffness discontinuity. With the web and spreader (See Section 3.3) closer to the LE and TE, the propensity for skin panel buckling is reduced in these regions. This same separation addresses web-buckling, as the x-shape can flex with the cross section. The implications of a reduction in web buckling include a lower overall blade weight due to less core material (and absorbed resin) in the web.

3.3 The Lap Shear Spreader

The regions of thicker core on top of the girder are an additional attempt at spreading out the lap shear in the bonds by providing a reinforced shear path over a larger area. This larger area increases the width of the bond layer, helping to reduce stress concentrations.

4. Summary of the Advantages

The shear flow pattern is changed through the introduction of an x-shaped web into the airfoil section as opposed to the traditional I-web or box-beam. The following are advantages:

- fewer lap shear stress concentrations in the bonds;
- lighter blades due to the reduction in core material in the webs and reduction of the amount of adhesive and absorbed resin in the blade;
- reduced propensity for web buckling;
- reduced propensity for skin panel buckling, and,
- closed section shear flow with lower magnitudes.

5. Figures

Fig. 1a - Traditional I-beam shear web design

Fig. 1b - Traditional box beam shear web design [1]

Fig. 2 - Shear flow in a traditional design [2]

Fig. 3 - The x-web

Fig. 4 - Shear flow in the x-web section

References

- [1] J. Chen, Q. Wang, W.Z. Shen, Z. Pang, S. Li and X. Guo "Structural optimization study of composite wind turbine blades" *Journal of Materials and Design*, Vol. 46, pp. 247-255, 2013
- [2] G. Fernandes da Silva and J.C. Marín "Evaluation of shear flow in composite wind turbine blades" *Journal of Composite Structures*, Vol. 83, pp. 1832-1841, 2011